

Hidden in plain sight: AI-driven steganography and watermarking for secure transmission of ophthalmic data

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: To explore the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in enhancing steganographic and watermarking techniques for the secure transmission of ophthalmic data. This study aims to delineate the integration of these methods into healthcare frameworks to ensure data confidentiality, integrity, and compliance with regulatory standards.

Design and methods: A descriptive and analytical approach was employed to examine the potential of steganographic and watermarking techniques in ophthalmic data security. The study reviews historical and contemporary uses of these methods and introduces AI as a means to enhance their efficacy and application in medical data transmission. We applied an example use-case of an open-source steganography application that performs both data concealment and watermarking to demonstrate practical implementation.

Results: AI-enhanced steganography allows for the imperceptible embedding of sensitive patient data within digital ophthalmic images, which can significantly obscure the presence of transmitted data from unauthorized parties. Similarly, AI-driven watermarking can embed digital signatures to authenticate image origins and signal alterations, aiding in forensic integrity and compliance verification.

Conclusion: Integrating AI with steganography and watermarking offers promising enhancements to the security and efficiency of ophthalmic data transmission. While these AI-driven techniques contribute to a more robust data-handling framework, their successful deployment requires interdisciplinary collaboration and continuous refinement to address emerging technical and ethical challenges effectively.

Introduction

The digital revolution has propelled advances in ophthalmic care and electronic health records with a marked influx of patient data. This burgeoning data milieu necessitates robust frameworks for secure and efficient data transmission. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) with steganographic and watermarking techniques presents a promising avenue for secure data transfer in ophthalmology.

Background

Steganography, the ancient art of concealed communication, and watermarking, the process of embedding identifiable data into digital media, have long been employed in various realms of data security.^{1,2} When applying steganography to digital images, the key technical process involves subtly altering the least significant bits (LSBs) of pixel

values to embed concealed data. For example, in an 8-bit color image, the LSB of each pixel is altered to correspond to the binary data being embedded. Since changing the LSB only alters the pixel value by 1 unit, the modification is minute and imperceptible to the naked eye, thus preserving the overall appearance of the image.

One compelling use case of steganography can be illustrated in the secure transmission of patient-specific retinal images between healthcare facilities (Fig. 1). For instance, physicians may employ steganography to embed confidential patient data within the pixels of ophthalmic imaging. The embedded data is imperceptible to the naked eye, ensuring the information remains concealed during transmission. Upon receipt, another ophthalmologist with the requisite decoding key can extract the embedded data. This method not only secures sensitive data during transmission but also ensures that pertinent medical information accompanies the digital imagery, facilitating a comprehensive evaluation of the patient's condition by the receiving ophthalmologist.

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Watermarking involves the integration of identifiable data into digital media, such as ophthalmic images. Unlike steganography, where the goal is concealed communication, watermarking aims to claim ownership or authentication. For instance, an ophthalmic center could watermark retinal images with a digital signature before sharing them with a referring physician. This watermark authenticates the image origin and ensures data integrity, as any image alteration would also alter the watermark, thereby indicating potential tampering.

The arrival of AI further augments these methodologies by optimizing their encoding and decoding algorithms.³ AI can analyze patterns and redundancies in images to determine the best locations for embedding data, minimizing the likelihood of detection. Moreover, these models can be trained to recognize and predict the least noticeable changes in different types of images, thereby tailoring the embedding strategy to each image’s unique characteristics. AI also helps in detecting and correcting any potential errors during the embedding and extraction processes, ensuring the integrity of the hidden data. Many AI algorithms and architectures have been used successfully for these purposes, including convolutional neural networks, generative adversarial networks, and transformer models, among many others.⁴

Potential benefits

The essence of steganography lies in its ability to obscure the existence of sensitive information within benign host data, thereby rendering the concealed information imperceptible to unauthorized entities. This layer of obscurity improves established security measures, rendering unauthorized access to sensitive data exceedingly challenging. When combined with conventional encryption techniques, steganography fosters a dual security mechanism. While encryption obfuscates sensitive data to unauthorized access, the veil of steganography conceals the existence of any such data in the first place, thus providing an added layer of security.⁵ The use of high-resolution imaging in ophthalmology furnishes an extensive capacity for steganographic embedding. The plethora of pixels in these images can host substantial amounts of concealed data without any perceptible alteration to image quality. Moreover, the adaptability of steganographic algorithms manifests a pathway to adherence to stringent regulatory frameworks such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability

Act (HIPAA).

Beyond encryption, the integration of steganography offers several practical scenarios where its application proves advantageous. For instance, during teleophthalmology consultations, ophthalmic images transmitted between different physicians can embed patient history and previous diagnoses within the image itself. This ensures comprehensive information is transmitted seamlessly and securely, mitigating risks associated with fragmented data exchanges or missing patient records. Additionally, in clinical trials, steganography can embed trial-specific identifiers and patient consent information within imaging data, safeguarding sensitive information while maintaining the integrity and confidentiality of the data.

Watermarking also presents a suite of benefits for ophthalmic data sharing. By embedding a hidden digital signature within images, watermarking facilitates data authentication and integrity verification. This can be particularly beneficial in multi-disciplinary or multi-institutional settings where verifying the origin of shared images is crucial. For example, in collaborative research projects, watermarked images can ensure that each participating institution’s data is identifiable and traceable, thus maintaining a clear chain of custody and accountability. Moreover, watermarking can act as a deterrent to data tampering or unauthorized sharing, as the embedded watermark signifies the legitimate ownership of the data. In the event of data disputes or a need for forensic analysis, watermarked images provide a verifiable trail of data custody and authenticity.

Alternatively, in scenarios involving patient referrals, watermarking images with patient-specific identifiers and referring physician details ensures accurate identification of each image. This practice prevents misattributions that could lead to incorrect diagnoses and inappropriate treatment plans. For example, when a primary care physician refers a patient to a specialist, embedding a digital watermark containing the patient’s unique information within their medical images allows the specialist to verify the source and authenticity of the images quickly. This added layer of verification can help safeguard against errors arising from manual data handling. And like steganography, watermarking algorithms can also be designed to comply with HIPAA standards.

Fig. 1. Patient data is embedded within a cover image (*Eye Institute of Alberta* logo) using steganographic techniques. The pre- and post-extraction images hidden within the cover file were generated using *OpenStego* (<https://github.com/syvaitya/openstego>), an open-source steganography application that performs both data concealment and watermarking.

Potential challenges

The use of steganography holds a set of challenges that warrant meticulous scrutiny. Foremost among these are the detection and extraction difficulties that the covert nature of steganography may engender. The embedded data, while securely hidden within host images, could pose significant challenges when it comes to straightforward retrieval. Errors in extraction processes may lead to incomplete or incorrect data retrieval and potential patient harm. To mitigate this, rigorous error-checking and validation protocols during the data extraction process are crucial. Moreover, employing redundant embedding, where crucial data is immersed at multiple locations within the host image, could serve as a contingency against data extraction errors.

The potential misuse of steganography for the unauthorized transmission of sensitive data, underscores the need for robust regulatory oversight and ethical governance. In a scenario where an unauthorized entity gains access to the encoding algorithm, sensitive patient data could be illicitly embedded within images and transmitted undetected. If not properly regulated and monitored, the clandestine nature of steganography could potentially be exploited for nefarious purposes, including data theft or fraud. To promote data privacy, techniques like circular arrays and secret keys, in addition to combining steganography with cryptographic hash functions and blockchain technologies can be employed.

Additionally, the impact of steganography on AI model performance is a pertinent concern. Subtle modifications introduced by steganographic techniques, while generally imperceptible to the human eye, can introduce noise that potentially affects AI models trained to analyze non-encoded images. This is particularly critical in medical diagnostics, where high precision is paramount. While capable image classification models should theoretically handle steganographic data effectively, any observed performance degradation might indicate areas where they require further improvement. To address this, it is essential to develop and implement steganographic methods that minimize interference with other AI algorithms, while at the same time improving image classification models to enhance their generalizability. If a classification model struggles with steganographic data, it may signify underlying weaknesses in the model's design or training, necessitating enhancements to its robustness.

Watermarking, when integrated into medical data-sharing frameworks, also comes with its own set of challenges. Typically, watermarking is designed to be imperceptible to the naked eye, preserving the diagnostic value of images. However, this imperceptibility could pose challenges in verifying the authenticity and integrity of the watermarked images without the appropriate decoding algorithms. Moreover, robustness against intentional removal or alteration is a concern. Miscreants could potentially devise sophisticated attacks to remove or alter watermarks for unauthorized data dissemination or falsification. Devising watermarks that are resistant to tampering yet non-intrusive to image analysis requires a delicate balance and sophisticated design.

Conclusion

The integration of AI with steganography and watermarking offers a viable pathway for enhancing the security of ophthalmic patient data transmission. Steganography facilitates the concealed embedding of sensitive data within digital imagery, whereas watermarking supports data authentication and integrity verification. Both techniques augment existing security protocols and contribute to a more robust and trusted data-handling framework. However, the widespread adoption of these technologies necessitates a concerted interdisciplinary effort. Rigorous research, standardization, and collaboration between ophthalmologists, security experts, and policymakers are crucial to surmounting the inherent technical and ethical challenges. As the ophthalmic community delves deeper into the digital healthcare domain, the meticulous

exploration of AI-driven steganographic and watermarking techniques is a significant stride towards a secure and compliant digital data transmission framework, that safeguards patient data.

Authorship

All authors attest that they meet the current International Committee of Medical Journal Editors criteria for authorship.

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AI-driven steganography and watermarking techniques offer innovative solutions for the secure transmission of ophthalmic data. By embedding sensitive information within digital images, these methods enhance data security and integrity during transfer. The integration of AI optimizes the embedding and extraction processes, ensuring minimal perceptibility and robust protection. This study explores the potential benefits and challenges of these techniques, emphasizing their potential impact in safeguarding patient data in the realm of ophthalmology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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